

OVERVIEW

The code in this package runs the simulations specified in the paper. It also constructs the figures presented. The code was written and executed on MATLAB version 9.10 (R2021a), using a Windows 10 computer.

The simulations are based on functional forms and parameters as described in the paper. No data is required, and results are entirely produced by the code.

All code and results should be contained in the main folder *simulation* and its subfolders. These subfolders are: *calibration*, *results*, *temp_results*.

The main scripts to be run are the following.

In the subfolder *calibration*: *docal.m*, *docal_grid.m*

In the main folder: *dothis_a.m*, *dothis_b.m*, *dothis_c.m*, *dothis_p.m*, *dothis_f.m*

DESCRIPTION

The scripts in the *calibration* subfolder are used to find the initial suboptimal steady state for a given set of parameters, and an initial grid that will allow for a first approximation of the results.

docal.m is used to find the suboptimal steady state for a given set of parameters.

docal_grid.m is used to find an initial grid for a given set of parameters.

The scripts on the main folder can find the continuation value matrix V , the policy functions, the full path from the initial steady state to the optimal steady state and plot figures.

dothis_a.m is used to find the continuation value matrix V , using the grid obtained before.

dothis_b.m is used to refine the grid around the values that are most interesting for the purpose of the simulation, i.e. the values on the path from the initial suboptimal steady state to the optimal steady state.

dothis_c.m refines the grid even further.

dothis_p.m finds the full path from the initial steady state to the optimal steady state.

dothis_f.m draws various plots of the full path.

INSTRUCTIONS FOR REPLICATION

Every script should be run from its direct folder as the current MATLAB folder, e.g. when running *docal.m*, *calibration* should be the current folder; when running *dothis_a.m*, *simulation* should be the current folder.

The file *fixed_values.mat* contains important values to replicate simulations (1), (2) and (3). These are in the form of a single cell variable named *fixed_values*. Each row corresponds to one of the simulations, in order.

The first column determines the functional form of the utility (variable *utype*, used in *define.m*).

The second column fixes the parameters of the utility (variable *param_ind*, used in *docal.m*; the parameters themselves are used in *define.m*).

The third column specifies if the initial point of the simulation should be the default suboptimal steady state (if equal to 1) or an extreme value (if equal to 2).

The fourth column overrides the bounds that the script automatically generates for promised utility W . More details in the next section.

The fifth column fixes the values used to refine the grid. More details in the next section.

The sixth column determines the value for initial promised utility W_0 in the case where an extreme initial value is used.

To start from scratch, delete all *.mat* files from the folders *results* and *calibration*. Choose a simulation number to replicate (1, 2 or 3). Keep this constant through the following process.

Step 1. Edit the variable *sim_ind* in *docal.m* to match the desired simulation. Run *docal.m*. This should not take more than a few seconds.

This step finds the default initial steady state for the specified parameters.

Step 2. Edit the variable *sim_ind* in *docal_grid.m* to match the desired simulation. Run *docal_grid.m*. This should not take more than a minute.

This step automatically finds reasonable bounds for capital, promised utility, consumption and labour and generates initial grids based on these. The method is bad at finding bounds for promised utility, which is why these are partially or totally overridden with the information in *fixed_values.mat*. The process for obtaining those values is described in the next section.

Step 3. Edit the variable *sim_ind* in *dothis_a.m* to match the desired simulation. Run *dothis_a.m*. This should not take more than a minute.

This step finds initial values for V and iterates until the associated policy functions (optimal consumption and labour for every value of capital and promised utility) converge.

Step 4. Edit the variable *sim_ind* in *dothis_b.m* to match the desired simulation. Run *dothis_b.m*. This should not take more than 10 minutes.

This step refines the grid around the values of capital and promised utility that are relevant for the path from the initial state of the economy (whether the default suboptimal SS or an extreme value) to the final SS. These values are already included in *fixed_values.mat*. The process for obtaining them is described in the next section.

Step 5. Edit the variable *sim_ind* in *dothis_c.m* to match the desired simulation. Run *dothis_c.m*. This should not take more than 2 hours.

This step makes the grid for capital even finer for the same range used in the refinement in step 4.

Step 6. Edit the variable *sim_ind* in *dothis_p.m* to match the desired simulation. Run *dothis_p.m*. This should not take more than 10 minutes.

This step uses the policy functions from step 5 to compute the full path from the initial state of the economy. The script also calculates the labour and capital wedges along the path.

Step 7. Edit the variable *sim_ind* in *dothis_f.m* to match the desired simulation. Also edit the variable *maxt* in the same file to determine the number of periods that should be pictured. Run *dothis_f.m*. This should not take more than a few seconds.

This step generates figures of the path calculated in step 6.

PROCESS FOR OBTAINING BOUNDS AND REFINING THE GRID

The following is not required to replicate the results since *fixed_values.mat* is already provided as part of the replication package. However, this section describes the method by which the values contained in the fourth and fifth column of the cell in *fixed_values.mat* were obtained.

The bounds for promised utility included in *fixed_values.mat* were obtained through an iterative manual process. Start by having these defined as [NaN;NaN] and run *docal_grid.m*. This will use the automatically generated bounds, since no override was set.

Look at output variables of *docal_grid.m*: *V* and *Vcon*. We want the lower bound of *W* to be low enough that the promised utility constraint is non-binding for the leftmost columns of *V*, but not so low that it is non-binding for several of those columns. *Vcon* provides a good idea of this (0 means non-binding). At the same time, the upper bound on *W* should be reduced to avoid having several columns of *V* filled with *-Inf* (it's a waste).

The values for refining the grid in step 4 were obtained in each case after completing step 3. With that step complete, it is possible to have a rough idea of the path to the SS by running the script *test51.m* immediately after *dothis_a.m* (initial values must be edited on *test51.m* if seeking to replicate simulation 3).

With this it is possible to run *dothis_b.m*, then *test51.m* again to have an even better idea of what the refinement bounds should be. This can be repeated until satisfied that the path lies entirely within the refinement bounds, with little room to spare so that the refinement area is not wasted on values too far from the actual path.

Because a different initial state will deliver a different path to the SS, simulations (1) and (3) use different values for the refinement.